

An Agile Approach to a Project Management Information System Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

Company X has inefficiencies in their business process that are causing bottlenecks in managing their projects. According to the company, the process of collecting project and client information, and sending it for approval takes at least a week to complete when it should be done in at most 3 days. They also do not have a systematized way of storing and retrieving information, as their data has been fragmented across multiple software programs. Despite the restrictions brought by the pandemic, we utilized an Agile Methodology in developing a project management information system that keeps track of projects, clients, tasks and work logs of the company. The entire development process, as well as all interactions with the client, were done online. We used Google Forms to collect data from the client after key sprints, and we used Discord, GitHub, and Trello as our main collaboration tools throughout this process. In conclusion, agile methodology allowed us to conduct a flexible approach as development is done through sprints. Online meetings were held with the client after every key sprint, and the necessary tools were used to ensure the successful remote development of the system.

KEYWORDS

Project Management Information System, Remote, Agile, Project Management

1 INTRODUCTION

Company X is a design and development management firm that is driven towards sustainability. They offer 5 key services: 1. Architectural and Engineering, 2. Interior Design, 3. Master Planning, 4. Development Management, 5. Sustainability Design and Process Assessment & Evaluation.

According to their company representative, their business process revolves around the use of Google Sheets, Google Forms, Performflow, and Clockify. Google Forms is used to collect and document project and client information, which is then stored in Google Sheets. On the other hand, Performflow is used for the accepting or rejecting of pending projects, while Clockify is used by employees to log their work hours once a project has been accepted. All project documents are stored in a Network Attached Storage Server (NAS) for storage and retrieval.

Throughout the lifecycle of a project, all information involving a project would have to be updated to maintain as up to date as possible. The company would therefore have to navigate through all relevant Google Sheets documents, review its contents, and update its contents accordingly. In the same way, the company would have to navigate through all relevant Google Sheets documents, as well as Clockify, to collect information for project data analysis.

After meeting with the client and thoroughly going over their business process, we listed down all issues that they are experiencing. Based on the list, we then identified four main issues that are ultimately causing bottlenecks to their business process. The following are:

1. **Lack of tools for a systematic data storage and retrieval process.** With their current setup, data would continuously have to be downloaded, updated, and uploaded to the NAS server, which takes an unnecessary amount of time and is also susceptible to human error.
2. **Laborious use of multiple software programs.** Using Google Forms, Google Sheets, Performflow, and Clockify causes inefficiencies in time management and overall performance as some processes may take days to finish when it should be done by at most 30 minutes.
3. **Lack of data normalization across multiple softwares and multiple sheets causes data fragmentation.** Using multiple Google Sheets increases the tendency of data being duplicated, thus making it harder for the user to collect and retrieve data since data is fragmented across multiple sheets.
4. **Lack of automation for data analysis.** A user would have to navigate through all relevant documents to collect data for analysis. This process is done every time data is updated. Not only is it prone to human error, but this also causes unwanted time consumption.

To address the issues of the company, we adopted an agile methodology, more specifically scrum, for the development of the web system. An agile methodology is an approach that facilitates flexibility as it not only quickly responds to changes in the requirements, but it also keeps the development team and the customer in close collaboration [1]. Scrum, on the other hand, is an iterative process of development where at the end of every iteration is the production of a set of functionalities based on the requirements [2]. Given the situation of the pandemic, physical interactions were kept at the minimum, thus making the development of the system fully remote. Part of the study, therefore, is to gather insight on the feasibility of a full remote agile approach amidst the pandemic.

2 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Project management is the “application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to project activities to meet the project requirements.”. It is a combination of processes, methods, and experience to achieve specific project objectives. At its core, it is concerned with capturing project requirements, developing and implementing management plans for the project. It monitors progress, manages project budget, and maintains communication with stakeholders and the project organization. With the emergence of technology, tools have been developed to aid in the implementation and execution of project management. A project management information system (PMIS), are system tools and techniques used in project management for disseminating information, assisting in planning, executing, and closing goals of a project management [3].

The use of a project management information system (PMIS) holds multiple functionalities and some of which are the ability to manage users, create a shared database, issue tracking, and generate project and defined admin rights. These functionalities are aimed for the increase of performance, efficiency, and productivity [4]. Another project management system, developed by Taghavi and Patel, uses a database with which information is stored and retrieved. Their system consists of a workflow management system and a task management system, where users and teams are assigned specific tasks, which they then document on [5].

A major effect caused by the pandemic to businesses has been the shift to remote working. Since 2020, around 90% of companies have been adopting an agile approach for their software development [6]. Agile methodologies focus on iterative and incremental development with the utilization of sprints. As such, it is flexible in its nature.

A research conducted by Camara and his team aimed to understand how Di2Win, an agile software development startup, would deal with the uncertainty of COVID-19 pandemic. The companies main problems were (i) to maintain the productivity of the teams, (ii) to define the tools needed to manage the remote work, (iii) to align expectations with that of the clients, (iv) to continue delivering value through cycles, (v) to maintain the employee welfare, (vi) to provide

the necessary infrastructure for all employees, and (vii) to coordinate the development process [7]. This was all done during four action cycles, from March 15, 2020, to April 22, 2020, with seven sprints in total.

Although there were still a few minor requirements that were needed to be evaluated by the client, they still gave good feedback about the progress of the project during the quarantine period and were satisfied with the results, one of them being the reduction of bugs through each cycle [16].

One of the key learnings was that during the action research, which was their method, the actions provided good results, insights, and lessons learned about how to manage the uncertainties related to the remote work during the spread of COVID-19. This allowed and assisted the team to improve the quality of the code, to understand project requirements, events schedule, in the relationship among the members, the knowledge sharing, and consequently the feedback from the customer about the work done [16].

The research question of “How Agile Software Startups deal with uncertainties by the COVID-19 pandemic” was answered through the use of an agile approach along with having action researches. The action researches which were implemented at the start during each cycle kept the company in track. Thus, to manage these uncertainties, it was necessary to promote socialization events, establish socialization guidelines, knowledge sharing, establish code development standards, shorten the distance among team members, provide access to production and test servers, define tools for different purposes, set a schedule of project events and meetings, conduct training and workshops and maintain constant contact with the customers [16].

All in all, the company felt that due to the flexible nature of the agile approach, they were able to work well throughout the pandemic.

3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

After properly defining the main issues of our client, we listed down 7 objectives that we will be using as a basis in determining whether the developed system addressed the problems of the company. The research objectives of our system are to:

1. To reduce fragmentation of project details
2. To minimize human errors and time consumption when inputting project details
3. To remove the need to redo an entire form when inputting incomplete project details
4. To alleviate the tedious process of manually calculating the man-hours sheet
5. To lessen the consumption of time when creating client number and project number

6. To reduce the consumption of time and the possibility of a pending project being overlooked when accepting or rejecting pending projects.
7. To reduce the probability of overlooking assigned tasks.

Apart from the research objectives that are directed towards our system, we would also like to determine the feasibility of implementing a fully remote agile approach amidst the pandemic.

4 METHODOLOGY

This section discusses the methods used during the development and planning stages of the project software.

4.1 Research Design

The methodology implemented for this research is a case study approach wherein it follows the format of having a problem, solution, and discussion of the results. This approach analyzes the current process of the client to understand and evaluate problems and solutions.

With the uncertainty and challenges brought by the pandemic, the most viable approach was the agile methodology as the condition of the pandemic puts us in limitations to physically meet and collaborate. The flexibility of agile allowed us to adjust to changing requirements from the client and, as well as constant iterations to the system [8].

Iterations were made across sprints according to the feedback of our client. We contacted the client every two weeks during the start and end of a sprint to discuss progress and identify changes within the planning and development stage of the system.

A sprint would last for two weeks and during the end of each sprint, we would present to the client the system and provide a feedback survey for that specific sprint to apply for the iteration of the next sprint.

With the limited physical interactions brought by the pandemic, we utilized the use of online collaborative tools and messaging platforms to communicate with the client and the rest of the team.

According to Ford et al. [9], the effects of COVID-19 pandemic on the productivity of software developers adjusting to remote work brought in some challenges and benefits that may affect the process of software development. The authors also mentioned the following different factors that affect productivity, such as the ability to focus, work autonomy and motivation, work environment, and work-life balance.

We would also like to mention our challenges in terms of remote development:

1. Connectivity: The communication between us and the client would be affected when there are technical difficulties or internet connection problems, whereas in an in-person setting, we would have a face-to-face meeting with the client without any lag or connectivity issues.
2. Communication channels: All issues or conflicts on the program during the development stage can only be communicated and resolved remotely via an online call, which becomes challenging for the developers when facing technical issues.

The remote setting fostered a collaborative work environment for the developers as they would have to constantly update the team regarding their progress in their tasks.

To adapt to these conditions, all communication and interaction with the client were done via Google Meet and Gmail to discuss questions and feedback regarding the system. We also used Google Forms and Google Docs to document end-of-sprint evaluations and feedback. During the development stage of the project, we used the following tools:

1. GitHub - collaboration software for software development
2. Trello - collaboration software for work management
3. Discord - main communication medium of the team

As for the database, we simply upload the database in our Discord server to maintain the most updated database for usage.

To measure the feasibility of an agile approach in software development amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic, we used the following artifacts for evaluation:

1. Backlog - The list of set tasks that we must complete during a sprint. Tasks are placed as “tickets” and tagged depending on their status. We determine the success and progress of the project depending on the completion of tickets.
2. Test cases - A sequence of steps to test the functionality and features of the system. The results during testing would then be recorded to determine whether it passed or failed the expected output.
3. Client feedback - All feedback given by the client is recorded through our end of sprint survey, which also determines the progress of our project whether we are able to meet the needs of the client.

These mentioned artifacts would aid us in ensuring that we have concrete and accurate information to assess the feasibility of our project.

4.2 Research Participants

The Operations Head who was the representative of the company was interviewed.

4.3 Data-Gathering Procedure

Due to the restrictions brought by the pandemic, we were not able to visit the office of the company to conduct face-to-face interviews. All data-gathering and meetings were done online via email and an online conference platform. We interviewed the Operations head of the company.

We also asked the client to fill up a survey to gather data regarding the business process and design phases of the company using the ISO 25010 Likert scale.

Through the implementation of an agile approach, the project was split into sprints. Each sprint cycle was set to two weeks and overall, the development cycle spanned to a total of 11 sprints. All tasks and progress of the sprints were recorded and tracked on a backlog using Trello, a project management tool that allows teams to collaborate and manage their tasks. During a sprint cycle, the developers meet with their scrum master twice, once at the middle of the sprint cycle to hold their weekly sprint meeting, and another at the end, where an end-of-sprint meeting was held.

4.4 Treatment of Data

The data and insights gathered from the client were used to assess the business process of the company needed for the design of the system. All data were documented on a Google document file and assessed by us through a group discussion for the alignment of the proposed design of the system. Test results gathered from the test cases were also documented and used for the evaluation of the research.

4.5 Validation

A prototype was developed based on the required specifications that were discussed with the client. We would then meet with the client after sprints 3, 7, 8, 9, 10, and 11, to show and let the client test the developed system, and answer an end-of-sprint system survey.

Ideally, we would meet with the client at the end of every sprint, however, due to the availability of the client and progress of the system, the every week schedule was not followed. Despite not being able to meet the client consistently through the early stages of the sprint, we were still able to gather feedback for every sprint through our end-of-sprint system survey.

In the end-of-sprint system survey, the client would rate the design of the system based on the ease of use and their satisfaction with the design through the use of the ISO 25010 Likert scale. The survey also included the time it took for the client to complete certain tasks.

The metrics used for the survey were a Likert scale, in which 1 is the lowest grade and 5 as the highest grade. The given scores by the client were then calculated for its mean score of each functionality. The mean score received from the survey would determine which aspects we would need to improve in the system.

After receiving client feedback and gathering the data from the survey, we would have a meeting with our scrum master to discuss our findings along with the progress of the system. It would then be followed up with planning our next sprint cycle.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 displays the total score of all the results collected from the client evaluations given after each sprint meeting. The criteria evaluated the following: ease of use, user interface design, reliability, efficiency, and functional suitability of the system. The criteria used for evaluation were based on the ISO/IEC 25010 standard, which is the standard for a product quality evaluation system [10].

Table 1: Client Evaluation Table

Criteria	Mean Score (Out of 5)
Ease of Use	5
UI Design	3.6
Reliability	4.3
Efficiency	4.1
Functional Suitability	4.2
Overall	4.24

As seen in the table, the mean score of the client evaluation is 4.24. The criteria of ease of use and reliability were the highest scores. Based on that, we can assume that the web-based system was straightforward to use and was reliable. With regard to the other criteria, user interface design scored the lowest.

Table 2 displays the results of the initial test cases that we conducted. The result of a test case would either be pass, where the result of the test matches the expected result of the test case, and fail, where the result of the test does not match the expected result of the test cases.

Table 2: Initial Test Case Results

Test Result	Number of Test Cases	Percentage
Pass	37	84%
Fail	7	16%
Overall	44	100%

In Table 2, we can see the data gathered by the quality testing team. It shows the number of test cases executed, which is 44. Among the test cases, 37 of them passed while 7 failed. However, those test cases that have failed went to retesting later on to ensure that all observed errors were resolved. Thus, what is gathered now is 100% of the tests passing.

During development, we also based the progress of our project on the updates given by each member of the team. The goal was to ensure that all tickets under the backlog are completed within the duration of the sprint timeline. By the end of the project, we were able to generate and complete 225 sprint tickets under the product and sprint backlog items.

The use of online tools greatly contributed to the process of the project during the pandemic, as it allowed easy collaboration and communication without having to meet up physically. This also further encouraged the team to explore other tools to improve the process throughout the project. Since all communication and development were done online, it was easier for us to document and take in feedback from the client. The pandemic did not only impose the use of online tools for collaborative work, but also improved our self-learning and critical skills amidst the challenges faced during the remote setting. As a result, we were able to overcome the limitations brought by the pandemic and conduct the development of the system through the utilization of online tools.

6 CLIENT FEEDBACK

The main and only recommendation given to us by the client is the improvement of the user interface design of the system. The client has stated in the past surveys that the design of the system should align with the branding and style of the company.

7 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

By implementing an agile approach for the development of the web-based project management information system of our client, we were able to create a system that not only meets the standards of our client, but also meets the goals that were set for the system. These include:

To reduce fragmentation of project details

Utilizing a MySQL database centralizes the storage and retrieval of business process related information. Doing this removes data fragmentation as the client uses multiple google sheets to store and retrieve data.

To minimize human errors and time consumption when inputting project details

The system is designed to validate user input to ensure that no required input fields are left empty. It also implements methods that ensure that there are no duplicate inputs. A draft

functionality is also implemented in the system to alleviate the user from having to redo forms in case any fields were left empty.

To remove the need to redo an entire form when inputting incomplete project details

The system is designed to keep drafts of project and client forms. This way, the user does not have to repeat a form in the case that there is incomplete or wrong information.

To alleviate the tedious process of manually calculating the man-hours sheet

The system is designed to retrieve project specific data from the database. The data is then processed and shown to the user via the interface. This way, they do not need to manually retrieve and calculate data for the project analysis.

To lessen the consumption of time when creating client number and project number

Through the use of a MySQL database, the project numbers and client numbers are automatically incremented by the database whenever a new entry is inputted, thus relieving the user from manually creating one.

To reduce time consumption and the possibility of a pending project being overlooked when accepting or rejecting pending projects.

The system immediately displays projects needed for approval, relieving the user of the need to go over their email and see if they have pending projects for approval.

To reduce the probability of overlooking assigned tasks.

In the same way as the projects for approval, the system immediately shows assigned tasks to a user, relieving them of the need to go over their email and see if they have assigned tasks to work on.

As such, each iteration throughout the development cycle worked towards meeting these goals that were set from the start.

To conclude, we were able to successfully implement a fully remote agile approach amidst the pandemic using the necessary tools mentioned previously. Implementing an agile approach allowed us to be flexible by adapting to unexpected situations with regard to COVID-19. Given its iterative nature, agile allowed us to constantly adjust the system to the liking of our client as major iterations were communicated and shown to the client, thus making us gain valuable insights on the recently developed system. As we worked towards our goals, we kept in touch with our client through email and google meet. We kept track of our sprint progress through Trello, and we used GitHub and Discord to ultimately collaborate on the development of the system.

With regard to recommendations, we suggest making the design of the system consistent with the website of the company. This is in terms of the user interface, as they have specifically mentioned that. Furthermore, we recommend using a tool for SQL collaboration such as SQL Server Management Studio to relieve the developers from having to re-upload the database each time there is an update in the database.

REFERENCES

- [1] Éric Germain and Pierre N. Robillard. 2005. Engineering-based processes and agile methodologies for software development: a comparative case study. *J. Syst. Softw.* 75, 1–2 (15 February 2005), 17–27. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2004.02.022>
- [2] Abhinav Chandrababu 2005, A Comparison between Agile and Traditional Software Development Methodologies
- [3] Project Management Institute. (2017). *A guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK guide)* (6th ed.). Project Management Institute.
- [4] Adamsoo, A. (2010). Web Based Project Management System. Retrieved 2020, from https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/16996/Adamsoo_Ane-Mai.pdf
- [5] M. Taghavi, A. Patel, A. Patel and H. Taghavi, "Web base project management system for development of ICT project outsourced by Iranian government," 2011 IEEE Conference on Open Systems, 2011, pp. 267-272, doi: 10.1109/ICOS.2011.6079292.
- [6] State of Agile, "13th Annual State of Agile Report" https://www.duxdiligens.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/13th-annual-state-of-agile-report_7_May_2019.pdf [May 2019]
- [7] da Camara, R., Marinho, M., Sampaio, S. and Cadete, S., 2020. *How do Agile Software Startups deal with uncertainties by Covid-19 pandemic?*. arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.13715.
- [8] Neumann, M. and Bogdanov, Y., 2022. The Impact of Covid 19 on Agile Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review. [online] Doi.org. Available at: [Accessed 28 April 2022].

[9] Denae Ford, Margaret-Anne Storey, Thomas Zimmermann, Christian Bird, Sonia Jaffe, Chandra Maddila, Jenna L. Butler, Brian Houck, and Nachiappan Nagappan. 2021. A Tale of Two Cities: Software Developers Working from Home during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.* 31, 2, Article 27 (December 2021), 37 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3487567> ISO/IEC 25010. 2011.

[10] ISO/IEC 25010:2011, *Systems and software engineering — Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — System and software quality models*.

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